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BEYCESULTAN EARLY BRONZE AGE I POTTERY GROUP IN THE LIGHT OF NEW DATA

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ABSTRACT

The beginning of the Anatolian Early Bronze Age (EB I- 3400-3000 BC), roughly contemporary with the Late Uruk period in Mesopotamia, is marked by the rise of small kingdoms whose exact character is not clearly definable because of the absence of writing. In this period, the cultural settings of the Anatolian Peninsula are rather varied and seem at least in part to reflect the large range of environmental diversity across the region, and the numerous imposing mountain ranges that act as natural barriers to interaction. Decades of research on pottery analysis have contributed to broadly define geo-cultural groups whose boundaries often coincide with major natural borders. This paper aims at presenting new evidence on one of these cultural groups, the "Pisidia/Lakes Region", through the chrono-typological and spatial distribution analysis of ceramic assemblages from ca 40 years of survey projects in the area. During Pisidia/Lake District survey, red or black brilliantly burnished, thin walled and shallow fluted pottery and amphorae characterizing the Beycesultan EBA culture was discovered for the first time in the region. Furthermore a comparison is made to other better-known cultural groups, and with stratified contexts from excavated sites in the western Anatolia including for instance Manisa-Gavurtepe, Beycesultan and Küllüoba. Brilliantly black burnished shallow fluted pottery from Manisa-Gavurtepe's early phases sign to the western border of Beycesultan EBA I culture. In addition to this, few examples of same type of pottery from Küllüoba excavations shows that, Beycesultan EBA I culture has also relations with northern regions.

KEYWORDS: Beycesultan, Early Bronze Age, South-Western Anatolia, pottery, transitional period

1. INTRODUCTION

Pottery is one of the most important artifact types for establishing regional chronologies and the distribution area of cultures, as well as determining the relationships between settlements since there are a variety of manufacturing techniques, wares, forms and decoration styles (Özdoğan, 1997: 380).

During the Early Bronze Age IA (EBA IA), which is also defined as the "Transitional Period into the EBA", characteristic elements of the Western Anatolian EBA pottery emerge). This phase can be correlated to the end of the Late Chalcolithic in Mesopotamian chronology, which dates between 3400-3000 BC. During this time period, even the powerful kingdoms in the Near East were already known (Badra, 2015a: 10, Fig. 4; Badra, 2015b:30, Fig. 3). Despite this, according to Efe, the Early Bronze Age begun earlier in Anatolia than in Mesopotamia (Efe, Türkteki, 2011a: 187).

In the succeeding period, subgroups with local characteristics become more and more apparent (Fig. 1). It was K. Bittel who mentioned these groups for the first time in the early 1940s (Bittel,1942:186). In the 1960s, following new excavations and surface

surveys, J. Mellaart and D. French refined the borders of these groups (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: 35,183). However, based on the results of recent research, T. Efe has brought a new perspective to the subject (Efe,2004:15).

Efe suggests that there were culture regions in EBA Anatolia that covered wider areas and pottery zones in every cultural region, which might indirectly point to the influential areas of the local authorities. Beycesultan EBA I Culture Region, which covers a wide geographical area in the middle part of Inland Western Anatolia, has its own pottery characteristics.

Beycesultan, which was excavated between 1954 and 1959 under the co-directorship of S. Lloyd and J. Mellaart, is one of the most important mounds in Western Anatolia (Fig. 2). The pottery recovered from the site played an important role in the establishment of the regional chronology.

Beycesultan remains the key site for evaluating the EBA pottery groups of the Elmalı Plain, in which Karataş-Semayük (west of Antalya) and the Pisidia/Lakes District are situated, where sufficient research has not yet to be carried out.

Figure 1. Cultural Regions Western Anatolia EBA IB and the Pottery Groups (redrawn) (Sarı, 2012:139).

Figure 2. Beycesultan and important settlements mentioned in the text

2. CHRONOLOGY PROBLEMS IN RELATION WITH THE BEYCESULTAN EBA I POTTERY

J. Mellaart states that, even though there are significant differences between the pottery groups of the Late Chalcolithic Period and the EBA I. The EBA I pottery developed from the L. Chalcolithic 4 (which is the top layer of the Late Chalcolithic) and has no

association with the arrival of a new ethnic group (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: 117).

Since Beycesultan is one of earliest sites to be excavated in Anatolia, certain chronological problems exist, especially in regards to the EB I period. Scientists carrying out recent investigations and excavations in the region and the immediate surroundings have brought new suggestions to this problem.

Table 1: Chronological Chart of M. J. Mellink (redrawn) (Mellink, 1992: Table 2-3)

DATES	NORTHWEST	SOUTHWEST	CENTRAL	KÜLTEPE ALIŞAR	CILICIA	GAZİANTEP	EUPHRATES	EAST	AMUQ
2700 BC? EARLY BRONZE AGE IB	Troy I Early Kumtepe Demircihüyük	Karataş I-II Beycesultan XIX-XVIII	Yarıkkaya Alacahöyük 9 İkiztepe	Alişar Mound 14 12	Tarsus EB I	Gedikli	Samsat Carchemish Aslantepe VI A Tepecik W 3 Hasek II 5	Van and Erzurum Area Sites	G
3000 BC? EARLY BRONZE AGE IA	Demircihüyük C-G Kumtepe	Beycesultan XX Kuaura A		Alişar 15	Tarsus EB I Early		Tepecik Hasek H. Norşuntepe Korucutepe Pulur-Sakyol Lidar Cist Graves Kurban		
3400 BC?									

Table 2: Chronological Chart of T. Efe (redrawn) (Efe, 2000: 36, Fig. 19) NB: According to Efe, well-burnished shallow fluted bowls can be dated between Kusura A and B (3300-3000 BC). The pottery found in the Kusura cemetery has not been found in the Kusura A settlement. For this reason, Efe dated this pottery a bit earlier. Since there was similar pottery found at Kusura and Kakkh Mevkii, the data suggests that these settlements were contemporary and date to the Transitional Period to the Early Bronze Age. In addition to this, unlike Mellaart, Efe dated level XX of Beycesultan to the Late Chalcolithic and XXI to the Transitional Period, as well as Phase D of Demircihüyük.

	LEMNOS	TROAD		ESKİŞEHİR PLAIN		UPPER SAKARYA		AFYON-ALTINTAŞ	
	Poliochni	Troy	Kumtepe	Demircihüyük		Küllüoba			
EBA III	Red		b						
2400 BC		II a		Hiatus		EB III Levels			
EB II		... j h-j		Q P O N		Megaron Complex		Kakkh Cemetery	
	Green	g f	Kumtepe	M L	Early Aharköy	AF-AG Trenches		Karaoğlan	
2700 BC		I e d	IC	K I H		1		Kusura B	
EB I (EB IB)		c		G					
3000 BC	Blue	b		F		2		Kusura A	Hacıhamza Tatarmuhat Arslanapa
		a		E					
Transitional Period (EB IA)				D	Kuştepe Y.Söğütözü I	3		Kakkh	
	Black		Kumtepe IB		Y. Söğütözü II	4	Taşlık Kırca Höyük	Kusura Cemetery	
3000 BC						5			
Late Chalcolithic	Myrina I			C		6			
	SOUTH-WEST ANATOLIA			POLATLI-SİVRİHİSAR		CENTRAL ANATOLIA			EAST ANATOLIA
	Beycesultan	Kuruçay	Semayük	Polatlı		Alışar	Alacahöyük	İkiztepe	
EBA III									
2400 BC	Hiatus ?		V 3						
	XIII a					8 M	7		
EB II	XII b-c		V 2					Mound 2 (I)	EB II
	XIV		V 1	I b	Bahçecik I				
	XV	1						Mound 1 (II)	
2700 BC	XVI	2	IV			11 M	12		
EB I (EB IB)						12 M			
3000 BC	Hiatus ? XVII XVIII		I-III	Hiatus ?		14 M		Mound 1 (III)	EB IB
Transitional Period (EB IA)							13		
	XIX					15 M		Mound 2 (II)	EB IA
3000 BC	Hiatus ?		Hiatus ?	I a			14		Late Uruk
Late Chalcolithic	XX XXIV	3 4	Bağbaşı		Çalca Bahçecik II	18 M		Mound 2 (III)	

E. Akdeniz, one of the researchers who carried out investigations in the area, supports Mellaart's thesis and suggests that the pottery in question absolutely developed from the pottery of the L. Chalcolithic, specifically the L.Chal. 4- 9. Furthermore, E. Akdeniz is of the opinion that the pottery from the Beycesultan layers XX/XIX displays characteristics of the "Transitional Period" into the EBA and these layers must be considered "transitional" from the L. Chalcolithic into the EBA I (Akdeniz, 1999: 321).

J. Mellaart states that the EBA I pottery is more specialized than the pottery of the L. Chalcolithic. Specifically, the EBA I pottery is thin-walled, brilliantly burnished and shallow-fluted, which is characteristic for the Beycesultan EBA I but is not encountered in the preceding L. Chalcolithic Period (Efe et al, 1995:373).

Taking J. Mellaart's view into consideration, T. Efe is of the opinion that there is a gap between the L. Chalcolithic and the EBA I, (Efe, 1988: 117) but the Kaklik Place and Kusura finds fill in this gap (Efe et al, 1995:374).

T. Efe explains the existence of the gap as the following:

The shallow- grooved and brilliantly burnished pottery of the Beycesultan EB I, which has been recovered in small number at Kusura, should be dated between Kusura A and B. The following are two arguments which led him to date this group to an earlier period:

1) The pottery of the Kusura Cemetery is not represented in the Kusura A- Group.

2) The graveyard pottery is less developed than the Kusura A-Group pottery, in terms of ware groups and forms (Efe et al, 1995:374).

Efe further states that Kaklik Mevkii pottery with its bowls that have an incurving rim, anti-splash bowls and baek-spouted jugs, as well as thin-walled, brilliantly burnished and shallow-fluted group should fill in the gap at Beycesultan as in Kusura (Efe et al, 1995:373).

Thin-walled, brilliantly burnished and shallow-fluted pottery, most of which is represented in black ware, has been recovered during the Küllüoba excavations. Küllüoba, which was carried out under the auspices of T. Efe, is of the utmost importance for comparative studies with the Beycesultan EBA I set-

tlement (Efe et al, 1995:25). During this period, new architecture and pottery traditions emerged. This period has been designated as "EBA IA" by M. Mellink (Mellink, 1992: 172, tab. 2) (Tab. 1) and the "Transitional Period into the EBA" by T. Efe (Efe, Ay, 2000: 36, fig. 19) (Tab. 2). According to M. Mellink, the last layers of the Beycesultan Late Chalcolithic should be dated earlier than 3.000 BC. She dated the Beycesultan XXth Layer to the EBA IA, which dates roughly between 3.400 and 3.000 BC, and proposed the timespan stretching from 3.000 to 2.700 BC for the EBA IB (Mellink, 1992: 172, 173).

In conclusion, J. Mellaart states that certain new forms, which are characteristic for the succeeding EBA I period were already present in the L. Chalcolithic 4, especially in layer XX of Beycesultan. These forms include bowls with incurving rim, single-handled bowls, two- handled vessels (amphora) and pots with sharply outturning necks and possible round bodies (Fig. 3).

No white-on-dark painted pottery, which is very characteristic for the L. Chalcolithic layers of Beycesultan, is encountered in Layer XX. However, in the later phases, a few white painted pottery examples have been found. Beak-spouted jugs and black burnished vessels with incrustation begin to appear (Fig. 3/13,14) for the first time in Layer XIX, which J. Mellaart dates to the EBA I. Bowls with incurving rims, single- handled bowls and pots with sharply outturning necks are among the forms continuing from the preceding period. Thin-walled vessels with shallow fluting, which are characteristic in the Beycesultan EBA I phases, appear from Layer XVIII onward. According to the re-assessment of the pottery groups from the L. Chalcolithic and the EBA I period at Beycesultan, it can be asserted that Layers XX and XIX date to the Transitional Period into the EBA. This conclusion was made based on the following arguments:

- In Layers XX and XIX, L. Chalcolithic and the EBA I pottery characteristics appear together.

- The characteristic white- painted pottery of the L. Chalcolithic Period rarely appear in the last layers of the Late Chalcolithic.

- The amphorae, the characteristic form of the EBA I, appear from Layer XX onward at Beycesultan.

Figure 3: 1-2-7-10-12 LC 4 (Level XX); 6 LC4 (Level XXX); 13 LC4 (Level XXII); 3-4-5-6-8-9 EBA I (Level IXI); 11-14 EBA I (Level XVIIIB) (redrawn).

3. CHARACTERISTICS AND CHRONOLOGY OF THE BEYCESULTAN EBA I POTTERY

Pottery of Western Anatolia displays more and more local characteristics from the EBA IB onward. According to the petrographic analysis on the pottery from recent research in upper meander valley, the local features of the pottery continued in EB II and MBA periods in the region (Semiz at all, 2018: 135). Pottery belonging to the "Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region" has been recovered in the Beycesultan layers XIX, XVIII and XVIIc, b and a. This cultural region has a distinctive pottery group in terms of wares, forms and decorations, in comparison to neighboring regions (Efe, Türkteki, 2011b: 216).

J. Mellaart classified the ware groups represented in the Beycesultan EBA I layers as 'Fine Ware' and 'Coarse Ware.' Coarse ware continues from the earlier period onward with no visible change.

Fine Wares, on the other hand, are already represented by a few examples in the earlier period (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: 117). Black/red burnished and thin-walled vessels of the Fine Ware type, which first appear in EBA I layers, are more predominantly represented than the other ware groups at Beycesultan. Brilliant burnishing and shallow fluting on the bodies of the vessels are among the most typical characteristics of this pottery. This decoration is mostly applied on the round bodies of cups, jugs and necked pots (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: fig. P.17/1,3; 19/5). The inside of the vessels are frequently wet-smoothed with a cloth (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: EBA I Red-black slipped and brilliant burnished ware with fluted decoration (redrawn).

J. Mellaart's Fine Wares are represented by vessels with surfaces in various tones of black, grey, bluish black, olive gray, salmon pink, orange red, light brown and brown. Beycesultan is the only center that we can see all of these surface colors together (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: 117). In addition, "*Plum-Red Slipped Burnished Ware*" of the Pisidia/Lakes District and Konya Region (Üstün-Türkteki, 2012: 55) are also represented, according to the examples housed in the Beycesultan Collection at the British Institute of Archaeology at Ankara.

Many forms are in close relation with those of the preceding Late Chalcolithic 4 period. Carinated bowls (anti-splash) or bowls with incurving rims, which appear in Layer XIX at Beycesultan, for the first time (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: Fig. P. 15/1,2,7,12,13,14,15,21,31,33,38) increase in number during the proceeding phases (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: Fig. P. 14/13; 15/8, 16-22). The examples of these bowls with single- or double-holed horizontal handles are encountered in the Beycesultan EBA I layers (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: Fig. P.17/4-5) (Fig. 7).

Figure 5: Characteristic Pottery and form of Amphorae from EBA I (redrawn).

The amphora form (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: Fig. P. 5/12, Fig. P. 12/4) typical for the entire Western Anatolian EBA I, appears during the Late Chalcolithic at Beycesultan and onward. The form shows differences in shape and decoration from those of the preceding Late Chalcolithic. The amphorae from Layers XVIII and XVIIb at Beycesultan are defined as rare forms and have thick handles reaching from the rim down the middle part of the body. For these black burnished vessels, the fish-scale decoration applied in reserved bands is very characteristic (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: Fig. P. 20/2,4). Sometimes the necks and the handles of the amphorae are slipped and the body has a barbotine decoration on an unslipped

surface (Fig. 5/7-9) (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: Fig. P. 20/1). Beak-spouted jugs of the Beycesultan EBA I are quite different from those of the EBA II. The slender ribbon handles on beak-spouted jugs are very characteristic (Fig. 6/1,3,4).

Pots, which appear for the first time at the end of the Late Chalcolithic, have globular bodies, their necks flare out sharply (Fig. 6/2) and they have frequently vertical lug-handles on the body (Fig. 6/6). Tripod-cooking pots rarely occur in the EBA I, except in the Troy-Yortan Cultural Region- around Beycesultan and the surrounding regions (Sarı, 2012: 150) (Fig 8/4).

Figure 6: 1-3-5 Beak-Spouted Jugs; 2- 4-6 Jars; 7-8 Pots with incrustated decoration (redrawn).

Beycesultan EBA I pottery has a rich variety of decorations. However, its percentage in the total ceramic is quite low. Except the vertical, horizontal fluting (Fig. 4), and concentric applied fluting (Fig. 5/9); barbotine (Fig. 5/8) and fish-scale motives in reserved bands (Fig. 5/7) and knobs (Fig. 6/1) are very characteristic for this group. The white-on-black painted pottery tradition continues from the Late Chalcolithic decreasing gradually (Efe, Türkteki, 2011b: 216). Incrustation (Fig. 6/7, 8) and relief decoration are rarely represented in this group.

The Coarse Ware continues from the Late Chalcolithic without much change. It has red or brown unslipped surface; the paste has often straw and stone tempering. This ware is represented by bowls, cooking-pots, pots, and baking platters (Fig. 7). Large vessels are commonly used for the child burials as in the Late Chalcolithic (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: 117) The last layer (XVII) of the Beycesultan EBA I ends with a conflagration. This marks the end of "**Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region**" (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: 136) and many local pottery zones of the EBA II emerge within its distribution area.

Figure 7: Coarse Ware (Level XVII) (redrawn).

4. SUGGESTIONS FOR THE DISTRIBUTION AREA OF THE BEYCESULTAN EBA I CULTURAL REGION

J. Mellaart states that we are not well informed about the distribution area of this culture as is the case for the Late Chalcolithic, since the EBA I layers are often sealed under thick EBA II deposits. J. Mellaart suggests the existence of orange-red groove-decorated jug forms on the borders of the culture as proof of “**Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region**” in the Upper Büyük Menderes Valley and in Beycesultan and Kocayaka in Denizli. After analyzing the vertical groove decorated pots found in Yenice, Northwest of Afyon, J. Mellaart determined the most

eastern extent of this culture. J. Mellaart also considers Aslanapa, located south of Kütahya within the Beycesultan Group on the Culture Regions distribution map. In this case, according to J. Mellaart, the most northern border of the Culture Group is the Aslanapa settlement (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: p. 133, Map. III).

According to Mellaart, the distribution area of the Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region includes the Upper Büyük Menderes Valley, the northwestern part of the Afyon province and Burdur, Yeşilova, Tefenni and the Korkuteli Regions, situated within the boundaries of the Pisidia/Lakes District (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962: 129,131) (Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Distribution Area of the Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region according to J. Mellaart (redrawn) (Lloyd, Mellaart, 1962:133, Map III)

In his doctoral thesis, D. French extends the distribution reach of the Beycesultan EBA I pottery starting from the Beycesultan and Kocayaka settlements, as J. Mellaart suggested up to a region cover-

ing all of the settlements within the Acıpayam, Burdur, Kusura, Altıntaş, Afyon, Hoyran, Beyşehir, Akşehir and Konya Regions (French, 1969a: 31; 1969b, fig.29 b3) (Fig. 9).

Figure 9: Distribution of Area of the Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region according to D. French (redrawn) (French, 1969: Fig.29 b3)

After carrying out surface surveys in the provinces of Kütahya, Bilecik and Eskişehir, T. Efe drew a more precise northern border for the “**Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region.**” The northernmost sites, with the typical pottery of the “**Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region,**” are Aslanapa near Altıntaş and Aizonoi (Çavdarhisar) in the Örencik Plain. The other sites in the Altıntaş area containing this pottery, include Hacıhamza, Tatarmuhat and Karataş II. The typical characteristics of this pottery fade out in the Tavşanlı Plain, further to the north, as seen at Tepecik, situated in the NW of Tavşanlı. T. Efe lists the Beycesultan EBA I pottery characteristics at the site as follows: bowls with incurving rims, reserved slip and shallow fluting. However, red burnished fine wares, which is characteristic for the Beycesultan EBA I pottery group, is not encountered at Tepecik. In light of all of this new evidence, T. Efe extended the borders of this group as far north as the

Tavşanlı Plain (Efe, Ay, 2000: 34-35, pl. 24,25) (Fig. 10).

E. Akdeniz states that the pottery of the Late Chalcolithic exhibits a quite homogenous character on the entire basin of Büyük Menderes. However, this trend gradually changes during the EBA I as the local pottery zones begin to emerge. E. Akdeniz named this new culture the “**Büyük Menderes Basin EBA I Culture**” (Fig 11). According to E. Akdeniz, this culture originated in the area around Beycesultan and Kocayaka, and then dispersed around the entire basin, as J. Mellaart and D. French already suggested (Akdeniz, 1999: 320). E. Akdeniz asserts that two additional cultures (Kusura and Aphrodisias) were formed under the influence of this culture. However, all the characteristic elements of this culture are not represented at these sites (Akdeniz, 1999: 321).

Figure 10: Distribution of Area of the Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region according to T. Efe (redrawn) (Efe, 2003: 98, Fig. 1)

Figure 11: Distribution of Area of the Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region according to E. Akdeniz (redrawn) (Akdeniz, 1999: Har. 1)

J. Mellaart and D. French placed the Pisidia/Lakes District within the “Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region” (French, 1969c: fig.29a), based on the sherds with fish-scales and barbotine-decorations collected from the surface of the Burdur Mound and pottery of the Beycesultan EBA I style found on the surface of several mounds in the region. However, no fish-scale or barbotine decorations have been encountered among the pottery recovered from the Ku-ruçay, Harmanören-Göndürle and Bademağacı excavations, as well as various mounds during the surface surveys over the last 40 years in the Lakes District. This doesn’t comply with what D. French and J. Mellaart suggested for the southern border of the culture (The EBA pottery of the Pisidia/Lakes District collected during the surface surveys carried out under the auspices of M. Özsaıt constituted the main body of my thesis completed in 2012. This pottery is evaluated with a new perspective in terms of its characteristics, pottery zones and its comparisons with the neighbouring regions. It is of interest that not a single piece of pottery with fish scale and barbotine-decoration is encountered in the studied ma-

terial). Furthermore, amphorae, squad jugs and shallow bowls from recent excavations in Hacılar- Büyük höyük EBA I levels in the region reminds us of Beycesultan EBA I culture. But this evidence is still not enough to identify the Pisidia/Lake District region in the distribution area of the Beycesultan EBA I culture (Umurtak, Duru, 2013:18; Umurtak, Duru, 2014:12).

Considering the neighbouring regions, apart from the distribution area of the Beycesultan EBA I cultural region, there is no evidence of parallel pottery types. No parallel ware groups or pottery types have been noted at Emporio, Poliochni, Thermi or Agio Gala, except for the usual types, such as simple profile bowls. The relationship between Southwestern Anatolia and the Aegean Islands has been known since the Neolithic and Chalcolithic, especially from the pottery. However, this relationship ended before the Kastri-Lefkandi I phase. For this reason, it is hard to say that there was a relationship between the two distinct regions during the temporal range of this study.

Figure 12: Lycia –Pisidia/Lake District Cultural Region and EBA Settlement Distribution

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the new excavations, surface surveys carried out in the region by J. Mellaart and D. French (M. Özsaıt conducted surface surveys in the region between 1972 and 2010, and excavated Harmanören-Göndürle cemetery between 1995 and 2005. The Kuruçay, Höyücek and Bademağacı excavations were carried out from 1978 onward under the auspices of R. Duru. Finally, Hacılar II Mound (Büyük Höyük) situated in the immediate vicinity of Hacılar has been excavated since 2011) and current research, it is now possible to re-draw the southern border of the **"Beycesultan EBA I Culture Region"**. As stated before, very few pottery samples of from the **"Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region"** have been found in the Pisidia/Lakes District (Fig. 12). The Beycesultan EBA I pottery characteristics include thin-walled, brilliantly burnished and fluted pottery. This type is represented by red slipped pottery in the Isparta region and black burnished pottery in the Burdur region (Fig. 13).

Figure 13: Pisidia/Lake District Beycesultan EBA I Red/Black Slipped and Burnished Ware (Üstün-Türkteki, 2012)

The simple bowls, bowls with incurving rims and pots with sharply outturning necks of the Pisidia/Lakes District display parallels with those of

Beycesultan. Since this pottery is represented by few examples in the Lakes District, all of it can be considered as imports in the region.

The Pisidia/Lakes District during the EBA I period contains a separate cultural region with its own local wares. The two cultural regions are separated geographically by the Söğüt, Karakuş and Sultan mountain ranges.

In light of the new excavations and surface surveys, it became clearer that there is a separate culture in the region (Üstün-Türkteki, 2012:123) to the south of the **"Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region,"** which is called the **"Lycia-Pisidia/Lakes District EBA I Cultural Region"** (K. Bittel first introduces the Pisidian Cultural Group. Bittel, 1945; Afterwards, A. Goetze shows a local group which he named the **"Pisidia Group"**. Goetze, 1957:20; Furthermore, the Likya/Pisidya Cultural Region was named by Efe, (Efe, 2003:91).

Based on the new research, the borders of **"Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region"** can be re-defined roughly as the following:

The northern limit of the cultural region should be delineated by the Kütahya Plateau. Further to the northeast, the border crosses the central part of the Phrygian Highlands all the way down to Emirdağ. The north of this border line is in the Phrygian Cultural Region. Typical pottery of the Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region has been recovered in small numbers in the Küllüoba EBA I layers. All of these must have been imported to the site from the southern neighbouring areas (Efe, Ay, 2000: 25).

The Akşehir Plain is the easternmost region where the characteristic pottery of this cultural region is dispersed. As for the western limits of the culture, certain characteristic pottery elements of the culture have been recovered at Gavurtepe near Alaşehir, situated 90 km west of Beycesultan (Efe, Ay, 2000: 19). As mentioned above, the mountain ranges of Sultan, Karakuş and Söğüt constitute a natural border between the **"Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region"** and the **"Lycia-Pisidia/Lakes District EBA I Cultural Region"** (Fig. 14).

New investigations in the region and neighbouring areas, which might be continued in the future, may change –to a certain extent– the borders of the **"Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region"** drawn in this paper. This important cultural region, with its own distinct pottery, covers a vast geographical area in mid-inland western Anatolia and without any doubt, played an important role in the cultural development and interregional trade relations of Western Anatolia.

Figure 14: Distribution area of the Beycesultan EBA I Cultural Region with light of recent research.

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